

2. Waveforms recorded during GLH feeding on susceptible TN1 (top) and resistant ASD7 (bottom) rice varieties using an electronic monitoring device, IIRI.

A fine (18 m μ), 5-cm-long gold wire was attached to the dorsum of an 8- to 10-h-old GLH female by silver paint. The insect was starved for 2 h and then placed on the leaf blade of a 30-d-old susceptible TN1 or resistant ASD7 rice plant. The gold wire was connected to the negative input terminal of a D. C. chart recorder. The voltage source was two 1.5 V D. C. batteries connected in a series. The

positive battery terminal was connected with the plant roots through aluminum foil and moistened filter paper (Fig. 1). The negative battery terminal was connected with the positive input terminal of the chart recorder. GLH feeding activity was monitored for 180 min at a chart speed of 1.5 cm/min.

The waveforms recorded for GLH showed distinct differences in the feeding

activity on susceptible and resistant plants (Fig. 2). On susceptible TN1, the GLH probed readily and ingested for longer durations from the phloem (Pi), although initially the insect also sucked small amounts of xylem sap (Xi). On resistant ASD7, the insect made brief and repeated probes followed by salivation and feeding mainly from the xylem. □

Yield losses of a susceptible rice variety to brown planthopper (BPH) in Korea

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We evaluated rice yield losses to BPH of susceptible and resistant rice varieties in fields in southern Korea. Susceptible

varieties were Sumjinbyeo (japonica) and Milyang 23 (Tongil hybrid). Cheongcheongbyeo, with the *Bph 1* gene for resistance, was the check variety.

Seedlings were transplanted in early Jun and grown using traditional cultural practices without insecticide application. The BPH population was recorded 55, 70, and 90 d after transplanting. Yields of each variety were compared with that of an insecticide-sprayed plot.

Sumjinbyeo and Milyang 23 had a large BPH population, but infestation on Cheongcheongbyeo remained low. Yield losses were 29.4% for Sumjinbyeo and 19.1% for Milyang 23 (see table). BPH did not affect Cheongcheongbyeo yield. □

Yield losses of BPH-susceptible and resistant rice varieties, Suweon, Korea.^a

Variety	Reaction to BPH	Insects/plant			Days to hopperburn		yield (t/ha)		Yield loss %
		55 DI	70 DI	90 DI	Initial	Complete	Insecticide free	Insecticide treated	
Sumjinbyeo (japonica)	S	0.4	47.1	503.4	99	105	4.1	5.8	29.4
Milyang 23 (tongil hybrid)	S	0.1	12.8	500.7	101	108	5.4	6.6	19.1
Cheongcheongbyeo	R	0.0	0.3	8.7	—	—	6.0	6.0	0.0

^aAv for 3 replications. DT = days after transplanting.

Field resistance to rice leaffolder

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Leaffolder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* is a major rice pest in the hilly region of U.P. Infestation from Aug to Oct peaks in Sep. We screened rice genotypes to identify sources of resistance.

Thirty-one entries for screening from different countries were received from IRRI. They were field screened in 1982 wet season. Forty-five-day-old seedlings